

Checklist for data publication – *Overview over files that are to be published*

	More Information	Description of file content	File Name / Repository URL
Collect	3 Collect		
Participant-specific information		Anthropometric data of participants (age, gender, etc.)	
General information		Metadata (software, hardware, background of project, etc.)	
Marker Model		Description of used marker model an anonymized picture of marker placement, if applicable	
Informed Consent		Information on informed consent for further use of data.	
Process	4 Process		
Metadata		Description of data processing procedure.	
Source code		Code used to process data or reference GitHub repository (include release or link it with a static Zenodo DOI).	
Readme File		Information on source code (contact information, release date, version)	
Analyze	5 Analyze		
Metadata		Software and statistical model used	
Source code		Code or scripts of statistical data analysis or reference GitHub repository (include release or link it with a static Zenodo DOI).	
Readme File		Information on source code (contact information, release date, version)	
Share	6 Share		
Licence		Licence applicable to the shared data.	
Informed Consent		Statement how informed consent for further use of data was obtained.	
Metadata		Description of the dataset, instructions for data interpretation, contact information, release date, version of the dataset Related datasets or publications	
Data		Necessary data needed to reproduce your work (raw or processed).	